

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

SSHOCingly good and sustainable tools

SSHOC Factsheets Booklet

April 2022

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SSHOCingly good and sustainable tools

SSHOCingly good and sustainable tools

In this SSHOCingly good and sustainable tools booklet we showcase the tools, resources and plug & play communities produced by the SSHOC project, through their dedicated factsheets. We start the booklet with the SSH Open Marketplace, and continue with the factsheets per category: Sharing & Discovery, Data Management, Processing & Analysis, Datasets, Training & Support and SSHOC Data Communities.

- ➔ SSH Open Marketplace

SHARING AND DISCOVERY

- ➔ Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph
- ➔ Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry
- ➔ ARIADNEplus Infrastructure

DATA MANAGEMENT

- ➔ Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS)
- ➔ Virtual Collection Registry
- ➔ SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro)
- ➔ Language Resource Switchboard
- ➔ European Social Survey as a Service
- ➔ SSH Conversion Hub
- ➔ Archive in a Box
- ➔ Aioli platform
- ➔ COORDINATE

PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

- ➔ SurveyCodings
- ➔ Automatic Verification Tool (AVT)

DATASETS

- ➔ "RAISE" (Restore dAta Integration Suite)
- ➔ Multilingual Technologies for Open Science
- ➔ The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires (MCSQ)
- ➔ CLARIN Multilingual Metadata

TRAINING AND SUPPORT

- ➔ The SSH Training Community
- ➔ SSH Training Discovery Toolkit
- ➔ The Trainers Directory
- ➔ Improved and FAIR data Repositories – SSHOC Trusted Repositories (SSHOC Trust Support)
- ➔ SSHOC League of Data
- ➔ Archaeology Data Service / Digital Antiquity Guides to Good Practice
- ➔ Religious Studies
- ➔ OPERAS
- ➔ Heritage Science and Humanities Data Community

SSH Open Marketplace

Discoverability and findability of research services and products are essential to enable sharing and re-use of workflows and methodologies and an important task for researchers from diverse domains within the social sciences and humanities. Yet finding and assessing such resources can be challenging in a dynamic landscape shaped by a multitude of agents and institutions.

The SSH Open Marketplace overcomes this challenge with its curated entry point for researchers from the Humanities and Social Sciences.

Description

A discovery portal for the Social Sciences and Humanities: The SSH Open Marketplace

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace is a discovery portal which pools and contextualises resources for Social Sciences and Humanities research communities spanning tools, services, training materials, datasets, publications and workflows. The Marketplace highlights and showcases solutions and research practices for every step of the SSH research data life cycle. The service is built following 3 key principles:

- ➔ **Curation** – because quality of (meta)data is key! The curation process relies on three components: automatic ingest and update of data sources; continuous curation of the information by the editorial team and, – most importantly, – contributions from users, the SSH research community.
- ➔ **Community** – Features that allow contributions and feedback are implemented to ensure that the portal mirrors real research practices. Hands-on sessions are regularly organised to support users and promote the service.
- ➔ **Contextualisation** – The portal puts all items into context: each solution suggested is linked to other related resources (e.g. a tutorial showing how to use a tool, a tool used in a workflow, a publication presenting research results produced using a given service).

Built as part of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster, the Marketplace is maintained by three European Research Infrastructures, DARIAH, CLARIN and CESSDA.

An Editorial Team ensures the day-to-day maintenance and the data quality of the SSH Open Marketplace. Liaising with the service providers and the end-users of the service, SSH researchers and support staff for researchers, the Editorial Team supports the technical operation, the effectiveness of the curation process and the editorial policy's successful implementation.

Key features

The SSH Open Marketplace aggregates SSH resources, with around 5000 resources featured at the date of the final release, coming from 15 trusted sources. The catalogue provides basic and multi-faceted searches as well as browsing options to explore the resources.

A detailed view of every item registered includes a structured set of metadata describing the resource, and highlights the related items to facilitate the discovery of relevant resources and foster serendipity in digital methods. Contextualisation and relations between items ensure that this discovery portal fosters serendipity in digital methods.

Sharing and
Discovery

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace

Discover new and contextualised resources for your research in Social Sciences and Humanities: tools, services, training materials, workflows and datasets. [Read more...](#)

Browse

Browse by activity

[Analyzing \(641\)](#) [Visual Analysis \(314\)](#) [Content Analysis \(250\)](#) [Discovering \(180\)](#) [Capturing \(175\)](#) [Enriching \(148\)](#) [Disseminating \(143\)](#)
[Annotating \(142\)](#) [Gathering \(123\)](#) [Creating \(116\)](#) [Publishing \(101\)](#) [Collaborating \(97\)](#) [Organizing \(94\)](#) [Sharing \(91\)](#)
[Network Analysis \(79\)](#) [Curation \(76\)](#) [Edition \(72\)](#) [Data Cleaning \(61\)](#) [Web Development \(58\)](#) [Communication \(56\)](#)

Last added

See what's new

[Bibliography of the History of the Czech Lands](#)

Community curation is a central element for the SSH Open Marketplace. With its user-friendly interface and log-in mechanism, it is easy for users to create or enrich content and as such, contribute to improving the (meta) data quality of the records.

The SSH Open Marketplace also includes an Application Programming Interface (API), which is open for anyone to use. Some of the functionalities are closed, but most are open, such as searching and retrieving detailed information on all items of the Marketplace (<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about/implementation>).

The SSH Open Marketplace is one of the key entry points in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) specifically designed for the Social Sciences and Humanities researchers!

Benefits

Thanks to the SSH Open Marketplace, SSH researchers can:

- ➔ Gain access to useful and well curated resources
- ➔ Find and discover new digital methods
- ➔ Easily understand and assess usefulness of a resource thanks to the contextualisation provided between the items of the catalogue
- ➔ Promote their work, e.g. by adding information about the tool or workflow they develop
- ➔ Get actively involve in the SSH community data curation routines, choosing to become a basic contributor or advanced curator.

More information

- ➔ The SSH Open Marketplace - explained the easy way - <https://youtu.be/4tyZ4vhrM9s>
- ➔ Buddenbohm, Stefan, Barbot, Laure, Gray, Edward, Willems, Marieke, Larrousse, Nicolas, & Petitfils, Clara. (2021). Requesting Crowd Expertise: The SSH Open Marketplace and LIBER. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4757290>
- ➔ Laure Barbot, & Edward Gray. (2021, September 29). Sharing digital tools in context: the SSH Open Marketplace. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5535742>
- ➔ Matej Ďurčo, Laure Barbot, Klaus Illmayer, Sotiris Karampatakis, Frank Fischer, Yoann Moranville, Joshua Tetteh Ocansey, Stefan Probst, Michał Kozak, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Seung-Bin Yim. (2021). 7.2 Marketplace – Implementation (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749465>

Discovery Portal

Sharing and
Discovery

Discovery Portal

- ➔ Alexander König, & Dieter Van Uytvanck. (2020). D7.3 Marketplace - Interoperability.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5871651>
- ➔ Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). D7.5 Marketplace - Governance.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>

Who made the tool

The concept, design and development of the SSH Open Marketplace has been carried out by SSHOC WP7 members

- ➔ DARIAH ERIC: Frank Fischer, Yoann Moranville, Laure Barbot, Eliza Papaki, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra
 - ➔ CESSDA ERIC: Carsten Thiel
 - ➔ CLARIN ERIC: Dieter van Uytvanck, Alexander König
 - ➔ PSNC: Tomasz Parkoła, Michał Kozak, Szymon Wolarz, Justyna Wytrążek, Ola Nowak, Eliza Kalata
 - ➔ OEAW: Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Probst, Klaus Illmayer, Seung-Bin Yim, Martin Kirnbauer
 - ➔ UGOE: Stefan Buddenbohm, Joseph Dung, Alireza Zarei
 - ➔ SWC: Martin Kaltenböck, Sotiris Karampatakis
 - ➔ CNRS/Huma-Num: Nicolas Larrousse, Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Edward Gray
 - ➔ CNR: Cesare Concordia
 - ➔ FORTH: Chryssoula Bekiari, Athina Kritsotaki
 - ➔ TRUST-IT: Marieke Willems, Leonardo Marino, Tracey Biller, Filomena Minichiello, Stephanie Parker
- and by our community of testers, especially: Agnieszka Szulińska, Maurizio Toscano, Kasia Karpinska, Vanessa Hanneschläger, Simon Saldner, Judith Wehmeyer, Ami Saji, Genevieve Michaud, Irena Vipavc, Veronika Heider, Jakob Lenardic, Melina Jander, Lukas Weimer, Nanette Rissler-Pipka...

Access

[Access via the EOSC Portal](#)

[Direct Access](#)

Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph

Challenge

Researchers in the area of Electoral Studies find it difficult to search for publications and get meaningful results. It is often the case that they misspell the publications' authors and get no relevant results. Typically, there is no taxonomy to help them guide the search. This means the researchers have to use many different sources and put together all relevant information they need in an exercise with high efforts.

What is the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph

The tool provides the researchers a taxonomy for navigation (information discovery) so that they can browse publications in different categories, which allows them a more systematic search. On top of that, the Knowledge Graph integrates different kinds of domain knowledge in Electoral Studies, in order to provide the context needed by the researchers. They can also find similar publications from the existing ones based on the metadata from the Knowledge Graph. Thereby information discovery, search and browse at a single-point-of-access for researchers in electoral studies become a reality.

Key features

- ➔ Search based on a Knowledge Graph (i.e., taxonomy and ontology) which allows for disambiguation
- ➔ Multi-faceted search based on a navigational taxonomy
- ➔ Contextualizing results and providing a more rich metadata based on the Knowledge Graph
- ➔ Finding similar publications, authors, datasets etc.

Benefits

- ➔ Single point of access for relevant information for researchers in the field of electoral studies
- ➔ More accurate search results
- ➔ Multi-faceted search based on a taxonomy
- ➔ Re-use of contextualized data via different APIs and endpoints
- ➔ Find similar results computed from a Knowledge Graph metadata
- ➔ Thereby reduction of time and efforts to find and use needed information for the daily work.

Tool

More information

- ➔ D9.7 Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies
<https://sshopencloud.eu/d97-design-and-planning-knowledge-graph-electoral-studies>
- ➔ D9.9 Delivery of user-validated Knowledge Graph, and Election Studies Analytics dashboard
<https://sshopencloud.eu/d99-delivery-user-validated-knowledge-graph-and-election-studies-analytics-dashboard>

Who made the tool

[The Austrian Social Science Data Archive](#)

[Semantic Web Company](#)

[University of Nottingham](#)

[University of Vienna](#)

Access to the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph

[Access the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph](#)

[Access on the Service Catalogue](#)

Sharing and Discovery

Tool

Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry

Quantitative surveys play an important and imperative role in studying and learning about the integration and inclusion experiences of ethnic and migrant minorities (EMM). Unfortunately, such data have not always been easy to locate or access for both research and policymaking purposes. The EMM (Ethnic and Migrant Minority) Survey Registry is, hence, a direct response to this challenge, as its main objective is to make quantitative surveys undertaken with EMM populations 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable).

The EMM Survey Registry is a free online discovery tool that displays detailed information (i.e. metadata) about existing quantitative sample-based surveys conducted with EMM populations in Europe. Jointly developed by SSHOC, the COST Action 16111 – ETHMIGSURVEYDATA (a network of 200 plus EMM researchers across Europe), and the French Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR)-funded project FAIRETHMIGQUANT, the EMM Survey Registry promotes the FAIR principles and provides a concrete example of how an interdisciplinary data community can drive the creation of a FAIR-friendly tool for the social sciences using a bottom up, collaborative approach for the benefit of a wide range of stakeholders.

The EMM Survey Registry is intended for use by researchers, policymakers, and other practitioners in their own research and/or policy-related activities. As a model of co-creation, it will also be of interest to data communities committed to making their data FAIR, to data curation actors looking to partner or connect with data producers or users for whom they can tailor their current data curation services, and to policy-makers working on open research and open data initiatives.

Key features

The EMM Survey Registry offers rich and meaningful metadata for each of the surveys it captures. Users are able to explore and interact with the offered metadata via the front-end of the EMM Survey Registry, using the following functionalities:

- ➔ Keyword search
- ➔ Simple and advanced filtering
- ➔ Summary of applied filters
- ➔ Sorting
- ➔ Abbreviated presentation of the metadata compiled for a survey
- ➔ Full presentation of the metadata compiled for a survey
- ➔ Exporting of the metadata compiled for a survey as an XML file

The back-end of the EMM Survey Registry is where all of the metadata are stored, organised, and managed. Users are able to request and obtain restricted access to the back-end, so that they can contribute new metadata to the EMM Survey Registry.

Benefits

The EMM Survey Registry is an innovative tool that:

- ➔ provides free access to detailed and structured metadata about existing quantitative sample-based surveys undertaken with EMM respondents
- ➔ offers user-friendly and user-centric functionalities that allow a wide-range of users to easily explore and learn from its metadata
- ➔ allows data producers to contribute their own metadata so that they can showcase their survey for free with an international audience
- ➔ is strategically designed so that it can adapt the type of metadata it collects and documents, as well as the ways in which users can engage with its metadata
- ➔ can support new research and policymaking needs by curating special metadata collections (e.g. COVID-19)

More Information

- ➔ [Methodology for creating the EMM Survey Registry](#)
- ➔ [Webinars/presentations about the EMM Survey Registry](#)
- ➔ [Conditions of use of the EMM Survey Registry and its metadata](#)
- ➔ [EMM Survey Registry back-end user guide](#)
- ➔ [EMM Survey Registry back-end video tutorials](#)
- ➔ [EMM Survey Registry's COVID-19 collection](#)
- ➔ [1st report analysing the EMM Survey Registry's metadata](#)
- ➔ [COST Action 16111 Ethmigsurveydata Zenodo community](#)

Who made the tool

The EMM Survey Registry is jointly produced by SSHOC, the COST Action 16111 – ETHMIGSURVEYDATA and the French Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR)-funded project FAIRETHMIGQUANT.

Access the EMM Survey Registry

[Access the EMM Survey Registry](#)

[Access via the SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

[Access via the Open Marketplace](#)

Sharing & Discovery

EMM Survey Registry

Tools & Services

ARIADNEplus Infrastructure

Challenge

ARIADNEplus is an extension of the ARIADNE Integrating Activity, which successfully integrated archaeological data infrastructures in Europe, indexing about 2.000.000 datasets. ARIADNEplus is extending and supporting the research community and further developing the relationships with key stakeholders, including most European archaeological associations, researchers, heritage professionals, national heritage agencies and so on. The new enlarged partnership of ARIADNEplus covers all of Europe. It now includes leaders in different archaeological domains like palaeoanthropology, bioarchaeology and environmental archaeology as well as other sectors of archaeological sciences, including all periods of human presence from the appearance of hominids to the present.

Tool

What is the ARIADNEplus

The ARIADNE Portal provides the main point of access for searching and browsing datasets and new services for processing and publishing archaeological datasets online. The Portal brings together existing archaeological research datasets from ARIADNE partners so that researchers can browse and access the various distributed datasets for use in their projects. The portal also provides a point of access for the new services developed by the project.

The datasets that are registered in the ARIADNE Portal catalogue are held by its partners and have been created through research, excavations, fieldwork, laboratory work and other types of projects. In recent years archaeologists have been increasingly making use of sophisticated digital equipment and techniques. During the course of a research project large volumes of data are created and collected, and become part of the research archive. ARIADNE aims to make these archives available through its portal for researchers to consult when starting new research.

The ARIADNE Portal offers a central point of access to the archaeological resources made available from partner institutions throughout Europe. Behind the portal lies the ARIADNE registry and a set of services that are used to manage information about the datasets, collections, vocabularies, metadata schemas and mappings. The registry is used to gather information about data resources and services, and to support the search functionalities offered by the portal. Partners provide a description of their digital resources based on the ARIADNE Catalog Data Model (ACDM), which is used to include the resource in the registry.

Key features

The portal offers users a simple friendly interface. It includes the familiar search box, which, once users start typing, it suggests keywords based on the content that is actually available. The keyword search is a quick and easy way of using the ARIADNE portal. Users who would like to browse the catalogue for content can do so using three starting points: Where, When and What. All three browse options are offered as additional filters on the search results page. Researchers can then use the filters to narrow their searches to a particular region or time period, and identify new areas that may be related to their research interests. Search results provide a list of the datasets that are available and how to access the dataset, which includes a description and a link to the content.

Users can browse the Catalog using the Where/When/What elastic search-based facets.

- ➔ **Geographic Search:** The first browse facet is a direct link to the ARIADNE Geographic Search Map. Users can find resources based on geographic criteria by clicking on the specific area of interest.
- ➔ **Advanced Timeline Search:** users can use temporal criteria to retrieve resources concerning a specific period.
- ➔ **Subject Search:** users can find resources by clicking on the specific subject of interest.

More information

[Guide to using the ARIADNE Portal](#)

Who made the tool

The ARIADNE Portal and Services were designed and created by the ARIADNE Consortium:
<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/partners/>

Access ARIADNEplus

[Access the ARIADNE
PORTAL](#)

[Access to ARIADNE
Services](#)

Sharing and
Discovery

 ARIADNE^{plus}

Tool

Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS)

There is no shortage of existing web survey platforms. Generally, along with user-friendly questionnaire design tools, they allow users to manage lists of contacts to which surveys may be distributed through different communication channels. However, for the fielding of cross-national high quality surveys, major shortcomings remain. First, access to panelist data should be confined to local national coordinators, and while it needs to be kept up to date, probably not all of it is appropriate to be shared with a third-party survey platform. Second, survey orchestration should be handled centrally (at the so-called 'headquarter' level), but without detailed access to individual panelist data. Third, contact modes with panelists not only must include both email and SMS, but they should be possible to freely intertwine during fieldwork: for example, sending an email invite and an SMS reminder.

A review of existing survey platforms showed that none would meet these three constraints single-handedly. Hence the need for a dedicated sample management layer that, paired with a survey platform, makes a whole that is fit to meet the needs of cross-national and centrally orchestrated surveys. That is precisely the gap that WPSS tries to fill.

What is a Web Panel Sample Service

The Web Panel Sample Service is a web application paired with the Qualtrics survey platform (with a tailored GDPR compliant license) to meet the specific needs (detailed above) of cross-national web surveys. WPSS enables centralised management of survey fielding orchestration (publishing, sending invites and reminders...) and decentralised and privacy-compliant handling of panelist data. Use cases can be found in the Social Sciences and Humanities (CRONOS-2 project) but may extend to broader contexts as well. A prototype of the WPSS has been developed and extensively tested in 2021 within 11 European countries. Starting October 2021, a new release of the WPSS will support its first full-scale use case, within the frame of ESS ERIC for its web panel spinoff of the ESS round 10 (funded under ESS-SUSTAIN-2).

Key features

- ➔ Multilingual support:
 - ➔ Panelist portals can be translated into the local language
 - ➔ All email, SMS and surveys are displayed in the panelist's preferred language
- ➔ Content editors drafting surveys, messages and translations thereof need not have access to WPSS and can be hired outside of the survey management team.

Tool

- ➔ Fieldwork orchestration actions (survey publishing, sending of invites and reminders...) are only accessible to users with headquarter privileges. However, headquarter users have no access to detailed panelist data.
- ➔ Users with National Coordinator privileges have access and are responsible for the accuracy of panelist data in the sample(s) they manage. This is made as little burdensome as possible by allowing panelists to edit a large part of their data themselves on their profile page.
- ➔ Email and SMS as contact mode, that can be freely intertwined
- ➔ Online user documentation is publicly available.

Data Management

Benefits

- ➔ Whilst the tool is designed initially for the ESS, it is developed to maximise the chances that other large-scale cross-national survey infrastructures will want to use it in the longer term.
- ➔ WPSS can be used in various studies where managing a sample and distributing surveys in a multilingual context and in line with the GDPR regulation is needed, for the SSH and many other domains.
- ➔ Adoption by users is facilitated by an online wiki.
- ➔ The software has been, from the very start conceived and developed with high software quality standards (sustainable, easy to deploy).

Tool

More information

- ➔ Report: [D4.1 A sample management system for cross-national web survey](#)
- ➔ Presentation: [Operating a Web Panel Sample Service \(WPSS\)](#)
- ➔ [WPSS online wiki](#)

Who made the tool

ESS ERIC HQ and Sciences Po, development: Sciences Po

Access WPSS

[Access to the Web Panel Sample Service](#)

[WPSS Instance in use by ESS-ERIC](#)

[WPSS on the Open Marketplace](#)

Virtual Collection Registry

Citing and Sharing Virtual Research Data Collections

A scientific publication typically includes a bibliography based on persistent references. Ideally any data sets used in the reported research are referred to with persistent references as well. Persistence of references to data has become a topic of growing importance for researchers, as more and more research data are becoming available online for reuse. Furthermore, the need for advanced ways to version, group, and share data - both within and beyond the boundaries of a single research organisation - has become paramount. To meet and support such needs, new concepts and tools have been developed.

A **Virtual Collection (VC)** is a coherent set of links to a set of digital resources (e.g., annotated text, video fragments, interview data, etc.) that can be accessed and cited for future use. The links can originate from different archives, hence the term 'virtual'. The individual resources referred to in a VC may have been generated by different researchers and teams, and usually, they are maintained at the repositories of multiple organisations. For discovery and management purposes, a VC is described by its creator with a set of metadata with preservation of the original access permissions. When a VC is registered in a **Virtual Collection Registry (VCR)**, it is assigned a Persistent Identifier (PID) so that it can be cited and referred to as any other data collection.

The VCR developed in SSHOC will support researchers in arranging and re-using existing resources and collections for new purposes, avoiding the need to create new datasets/corpora for every project.

The VCR was originally created by CLARIN as a service to enable researchers, lecturers, and students to easily collect, group and share virtual collections of language materials and is further developed in SSHOC to also support users working with other data types.

How does the Virtual Collection Registry work

The Virtual Collection Registry offers researchers user-friendly support for referencing research data that may be heterogeneous and hosted at different repositories. After authentication, users can create and publish VCs that will remain linked to their identity, whereas unauthenticated users can only browse and search published VCs.

The VCR also offers an API for tight integration with, for instance, repository software. Such integration allows users to create and extend VCs directly from the repository user interface and avoids the use of copy and paste when creating VCs.

Virtual Collection Registry

Software

Currently, CLARIN operates a Virtual Collection Registry that allows the creation and management of VCs through a user-friendly graphical interface and API. The VCR is one of the thematic services registered at the EOSC portal and therefore available also for disciplinary communities beyond SSH.

Benefits

- ➔ The Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) helps researchers to create persistently, identifiable Virtual Collections (VCs) for citing/referencing heterogeneous and distributed research data.
- ➔ The VCR enables researchers to access and reuse large samples of data generated by others in the context of a specific research project.
- ➔ The VCR facilitates the preparation of sets of resources for specific workflows and makes it possible to share and to work collaboratively on distributed datasets.
- ➔ The VCR personal workspace allows researchers to keep track of the steps taken in their research process and data selections used.

More information

CLARIN material

- ➔ Information page: [What is a Virtual Collection?](#)
- ➔ User manual: [Virtual Collection Registry](#)

SSHOC material

- ➔ Factsheets on GitHub: [Detailed VCR user guide](#)

Access the VCR

[Access the VCR directly](#)

[Access via the SSH Open Marketplace](#)

[Access via the EOSC Portal](#)

Data Management

Virtual Collection Registry

Software

SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro)

Cultural and scientific data cannot be understood without knowledge about the provenance (the origin, context or history). Provenance provides a critical foundation for assessing authenticity, enabling trust, and allowing reproducibility. Provenance metadata are data describing objects, people, places, times which are causally related by events. They are event centric and must be described in a historical order to ensure that there are no references to non-existent (non-recorded) events or objects. Nowadays provenance has become even more critical in the web environment where data are sourced not only from established archives, but from many mixed credentialed providers.

What is SSHOCro

The SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro) proposes an ontological model and RDF schema to be used as a top-level ontology for organizing knowledge and information found distributed across various primary sources of information in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC). It provides a semantic interoperability framework for the description of the data life cycle used by Social Science and Humanities researchers.

Key features

- ➔ a conceptual model is offered, that can be used to (re)describe at a generic level the real-world lifecycle of creating, finding and using data etc
- ➔ the use of such a model and schema can be applied as a standard to be used in the step of devising and implementing metadata capture scheme for tracking the data lifecycle in individual projects, institutions and disciplines
- ➔ it can also be used to map, transform and integrate existing data across projects, institutions and disciplines into interoperable pools of information for reuse and exploitation
- ➔ the ontological model tries to capture the tools and services used by research communities across the Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines at each point in the data lifecycle

Benefits

- ➔ SSHOCro is modelled as an extension of CIDOC CRM, which provides a common and extensible semantic framework that any procedural information can be mapped to
- ➔ Instances of the CIDOC-CRM model can be combined to huge meaningful networks of knowledge about e.g. historical facts and contextual relationships

SSHOC
Reference
Ontology

Framework

More information

- ➔ [Deliverable D4.18 SSHOCro v.1.0 beta version](#)
- ➔ [Milestone 20 Selection of SSH metadata standards for mapping to SSHOCro](#)
- ➔ [D4.19 Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro](#)
- ➔ [Presentation on The SSHOC Reference Ontology](#)
- ➔ [Workshop notes from Session 1: The SSHOC Reference Ontology \(SSHOCro\): Modeling the SSHOC data life cycle](#)

Who made the ontology

Athina Kritsotaki, Chrysoula Bekiari and Eleni Tsouloucha from FORTH worked on the development of the ontology.

Access the SSHOCro

[Access the SSHOCro on the SSH Open Marketplace](#)

Data
Management

SSHOC
Reference
Ontology

Framework

Language Resource Switchboard

Matching tools and data

Researchers in the Social Science and Humanities who work with digital data, often find themselves in a landscape with a large variety of resources, which makes it difficult to identify suitable data, tools or software that match their specific research requirements.

The general need for guidance and recommendation is addressed by catalogues, such as the [EOSC Marketplace](#) or the [SSH Open Marketplace](#). But successful searching in catalogues relies, to a large extent, on the ability of individual researchers to abstract away from their specific information needs and to understand the relevance of resources with a wider applicability. For researchers it would be more convenient to be able to start the search for suitable tools with what they easily have at hand: representative snippets or fragments of content. This functionality is offered by the **Language Resource Switchboard**.

By making use of the formal information about the data input (format type, language, date of creation, etc.) the Switchboard makes it possible to automatically identify the tools that match the data. In order to limit the number of suggestions in a meaningful way, additional filtering can be made available to allow the user to take into account research-discipline specific features and the context of the disciplinary provenance or usage of a tool.

How does the Switchboard work

The researcher uploads a representative snippet of data to the Switchboard user interface. The Switchboard “recognises” the presented data (usually a file with text, audio, video, etc.) and assembles a list of tools, software or web services that - given the data format, language, etc.- may be suited for processing the uploaded data. To support the selection from this tool list, the Switchboard categorises the results with a task-specific layer, indicating which type of process the tool can perform. For example: morphological analysis, sentiment analysis, or visualisation of geographic data.

A user can either start from a file, specify a URL or copy/paste a text fragment. Once the data has been uploaded, an information pane appears with the information that has been detected for the input data and a list of the matching tools. The user can then click on any tool to get additional information and open the selected tool in a new browser tab.

The Switchboard was originally developed by CLARIN as the Language Resource Switchboard as support for the selection of tools to process language data. [SSHOC](#) is working on extending the Switchboard service to ensure it is suitable for a wide range of users and data types by optimizing the filtering of services and the selection options. In addition the Switchboard will be integrated into key services and components from other service providers. The Switchboard is one of the thematic services registered at the EOSC portal and therefore visible also for disciplinary communities not participating in SSHOC.

Language
Resource
Switchboard

Software

Benefits

- ➔ The Switchboard helps researchers to find and start tools that are suited for their research data.
- ➔ The [Switchboard Tool Inventory](#) provides a complete list of all tools that are taken into account by the Switchboard matching engine.
- ➔ As a special application, the Switchboard offers a few general dictionaries and look-up services that allow the user to translate or clarify selected text tokens. Repository or catalogue managers can configure the Switchboard to include new dictionary services.
- ➔ New tools for integration into the Switchboard may be suggested following the step-by-step documentation under the [Switchboard Tool Registry](#). This is of particular interest for providers of tools and software who are interested in increasing the visibility and usage of their tools and services. The Switchboard Tool Inventory is growing and will include tools from an increasing number of research domains.

More information

CLARIN materials

- ➔ GitLab: [Switchboard Tool Registry](#)
- ➔ GitHub: [Switchboard technical documentation repository](#)
- ➔ Language Resources Switchboard: [FAQs & How To](#)
- ➔ CLARIN use case: [From language data to insight](#)

SSHOC material

- ➔ Factsheets on GitLab: [SSHOC Language Resource Switchboard](#)
- ➔ Factsheets on GitHub:
 - ➔ [SSHOC Language Resource Switchboard](#)
 - ➔ [Virtual Collection Registry](#)
- ➔ Open GitHub Repository: [Switchboard tutorials](#)

Access the Language Resource Switchboard

[Direct Access](#)

[Access via the SSH Open Marketplace](#)

[Access via the EOSC Portal](#)

Data Management

Language Resource Switchboard

Software

European Social Survey as a Service

The European Social Survey (ESS) is a cross-national survey based on scientific standards that has been conducted every two years since 2001. The ESS collects data on attitudes and behaviour patterns of the population in more than 30 European countries. The survey data are provided by the ESS-ERIC (ERIC = European Research Infrastructure Consortium). In cooperation with national institutions, data from interviews on attitudes, beliefs and behavioural patterns are collected throughout Europe.

ESS data curation, dissemination and storage have been moved to the cloud. The FAIRness of ESS data holdings has increased through a powerful search tool, automated data processing, increased compliance with standards, controlled vocabularies and persistent identifiers as well as more interoperable metadata.

The new ESS data and metadata service consists of multiple data and metadata repositories to support an efficient, collaborative, version-controlled data archive workflow. The service makes use of the Colectica software solutions for metadata management and the Azure cloud for data storage and management. The repositories are accessed via ESS API for management and dissemination of data and metadata.

The Colectica software solutions and cloud storage for data enables powerful data search, analysis, visualization and download services by adhering to the DDI Lifecycle Metadata Standard. The new ESS service has made ESS data more findable – for humans and machines. DOIs at study and dataset levels allow easier data reuse.

Key features

The system interconnects existing and new infrastructures. The NSD-developed APIs, which connect the repositories, make them effective tools for the storage and dissemination of ESS data and metadata. Furthermore, the APIs allow data curators to process, document and publish data and metadata in a secure and stable environment. The APIs have been designed to enable replacement of single elements without breaking the system.

Benefits

- ➔ Easier access to data/metadata for ESS users (e.g. researchers and students)
- ➔ Easier data retrieval and better options for reuse of data through implementation of FAIR data principles (automated data processing, powerful search tool, more use of persistent identifiers and more interoperable metadata)
- ➔ Reduced processing costs / time
- ➔ Less dependence on resource providers (licensed statistical packages, on-premises servers).

Who made the tool

[Norwegian Centre for Research Data \(NSD\)](#)

[Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research \(Sikt\)¹](#).

Data
Management

Access the European Social Survey

[Access the ESS](#)

[Access the ESS on the SSH
Open Marketplace](#)

European
Social
Survey

Dataset

¹ As from 01.01.2022, NSD is integrated into a new organisation: Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research.

[in /company/sshoc](#)

[@SSHOpenCloud](#)

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"Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782

SSH Conversion Hub

Making data FAIR requires agreeing on common standards and procedures for data management. At this point, the social sciences and humanities (SSH) research communities are diverse in terms of data types, metadata standards and data formats. Each community has its own established traditions. This diversity causes interoperability issues between the communities. Thus, suggesting and providing conversion solutions for recommended metadata standards and data formats used in the SSH is key to facilitate FAIRness of data, and particularly, interoperability between research communities.

What is the SSH Conversion Hub?

The SSH Conversion Hub is a registry that enables researchers to find solutions to convert metadata and data from one format to another. The Hub contains information about available conversion services and guidance for conversion workflows. It has both a human-readable user interface and an Application Programming Interface (API) for machines. The platform enables users to find appropriate conversion solutions, use them, and refer to them.

Key features

The main goal of the Conversion Hub is providing a registry of (meta)data conversion services and encompassing links to recommendations for increased interoperability. The Conversion Hub is based on a data model developed by the SSHOC Task 3.5 team, and the Hub is built upon version 9 of CMS Drupal. Key features were implemented mainly based on either functions available in Drupal core or by integrating modules from the Drupal ecosystem.

Benefits

- ➔ Enhanced findability of existing conversion solutions helps researchers to locate and access existing SSH metadata and data conversion solutions.
- ➔ Versatile search options and use of vocabularies make searching solutions quick and effective.
- ➔ The Conversion Hub provides curated information.
- ➔ The data model has been aligned with the SSH Open Marketplace to allow easy integration and interoperability.

More information

- ➔ [SSHOC D3.1 Report on SSHOC \(meta\)data interoperability problems](#)
- ➔ [MS14 Inventory of existing \(meta-\)data format interoperability solutions](#)
- ➔ [D3.6 Report on SSHOC format interoperability solution services, including new software](#)

Who made the tool

The Conversion Hub has been implemented and is hosted by DARIAH/OEAW ACDH-CH (Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage). The design and content is created by the SSHOC Task 3.5 team: Mari Kleemola (CESSDA-FSD), Katja Moilanen (CESSDA-FSD), Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Matej Ďurčo (DARIAH/OEAW), Klaus Illmayer (DARIAH/OEAW), Maurizio Sanesi (CNR), Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (CNR), Hervé L'Hours (CESSDA/UKDS), Benjamin Mathers (CESSDA/UKDS), Johan Fihn Marberg (CESSDA/SND), Eleni Tsoulouha (FORTH), Athina Kritsotaki (FORTH) and Cesare Concordia (CNR/ISTI).

Access the SSH Conversion Hub

[Access the SSH Conversion Hub](#)

[Access via the Service Catalogue](#)

Data Management

Tool

Storage

Archive in a Box

It is often a challenge for starting organisations to install a data repository for their designated communities due to a lack of experience and a lack of technical personnel. SSHOC developed the Archive in a Box based on the open source repository software Dataverse. The Archive in a Box makes the installation of the repository software much easier.

What is the Archive in a Box

The Archive in a Box is a software package intended for (research) organisations which want to run their own instance of a community-based data repository to make their data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). The idea behind the Archive in a Box is simple: it provides an automatic installation and setting up of the complete infrastructure without any extra efforts.

Key features

- ➔ Fully automatic Dataverse deployment on the selected domain name with automatically generated security certificates.
- ➔ The configuration is automatic so administrators don't have to modify files in the software package themselves.
- ➔ Various Dataverse distributions allow the provision of services for different use cases and the usage of custom components.
- ➔ Externally controlled vocabulary support.
- ➔ Support of custom metadata schemes.

Benefits

- ➔ Easy set-up of a data repository for FAIR data management and data sharing.
- ➔ Automatic installation and setting up of the complete infrastructure without any extra effort.
- ➔ Open-source software.

More information

- ➔ More information is available in SSHOC Deliverable D5.5
- ➔ Webinars about the dataverse software are available at the [SSHOC website](#).
- ➔ A user guide for the end-users of the repository is available on [Zenodo](#).

Who developed the tool

KNAW/DANS (CESSDA), AUSSDA/University of Vienna (CESSDA), University of Tromsø (CLARIN), CNR (E-HRIS), Universität Göttingen (DARIAH), PSNC (DARIAH)

Archive in a Box

Software

Author

Marion Wittenberg (DANS)

Access Archive in a Box

[Direct Access](#)

[Access via SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

Storage

Archive in a Box

Software

[in /company/sshoc](#)

[@SSHOpenCloud](#)

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sshopencloud.com

"Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782

I Aioli-platform

The management of multi-dimensional and multi-format data for documenting cultural heritage artefacts induces new challenges, such as the development of relevant analysis and interpretation methods, the sharing and correlation of heterogeneous data among several actors and contexts, and the centralised archiving of documentation results for long-term preservation purposes.

Therefore, managing heterogeneous data raises the need for a stable denominator (from a conceptual and technical point of view) for structuring data and annotations coming from a continuous process of observation and analysis carried out by multiple actors.

What is the Aioli platform

The Aioli platform is an innovative web service for the reality-based 3D annotation and large-scale collaborative documentation of heritage artefacts. The existing Aioli platform has been significantly upgraded in terms of technical robustness, the collaboration framework was provided, the management of controlled vocabularies and compatibility with CIDOC-CRM was established. A facility for visualising hypothetical reconstructions of archaeological sites was also added.

Key features

- ➔ The platform generates a dynamic 3D morphologic scaffolding for structuring data and annotations.
- ➔ This data structure becomes a way of enabling the communication between several actors involved in the documentation and the study of the same object.
- ➔ The platform interlinks all phases that characterise the overall documentation process within an “informative continuum”.
- ➔ It combines a continuous 3D mapping and annotation process, a morphology-based documentation framework and a flexible & scalable technology.
- ➔ The program combines the onsite retrieval of structured information according to the physical object’s annotation and the onsite collection and processing of new data to be spatially referenced and semantically correlated with previous data.

Benefits

- ➔ The interface for Aïoli eases the collaborative work on shared projects, by adopting a social network-like approach for the user-end uses.
- ➔ The collaborative documentation of cultural heritage is accessible via web interfaces from PCs, tablets and smartphones online and onsite, because modern technological components were integrated within a cloud infrastructure.
- ➔ The platform integrates controlled vocabularies in SKOS Standard through the development of a portable and lightweight component for the visualization, search and term selection, linked to the thesaurus management software Opentheso.
- ➔ The definition of a mapping mechanism between the "Aïoli" classes and attributes with the CIDOC CRM Ontology and CRM Digital compatible extension ensures full traceability of the Aïoli "2D/3D collaborative annotation framework", the description of the photogrammetric process and heritage information.

More information

- ➔ Report: [Specification of the new features of the Aïoli platform](#)
- ➔ Presentation by De Luca, Livio. [Aïoli a reality-based 3D annotation for the collaborative documentation of heritage artefacts.](#)

Who made the tool

Research and development team: Livio DE LUCA, Adeline MANUEL, Violette ABERGEL, Anthony PAMART, Pascal BENISTANT, Anas ALAOUÏ M'DARHRI

Community manager: Ariane NEROUOLIDIS

Access Aïoli

[Presentation of the Aïoli platform](#)

[SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

[Aïoli platform on the Open Marketplace](#)

Data Management

aïoli

Tool

COORDINATE

[COhort cOMmunity Research and Development Infrastructure Network for Access Throughout Europe](#) – a Starting Community grant funded by the European Union under Horizon 2020

What is COORDINATE?

- ➔ Initiates a community of researchers working to enhance child wellbeing
- ➔ Facilitates improved access to longitudinal survey data on child wellbeing
- ➔ Gives children a voice in research that concerns them

The COORDINATE project mobilises the community of researchers and organisations that will drive forwards the coordinated development of comparative birth cohort panel and associated survey research in Europe which focus on children's well-being.

The infrastructural community network brought together by COORDINATE will promote the harmonisation of and improve access to international survey data, in particular panel survey data, in the study of children and young people's well-being as they grow up.

The research that COORDINATE will complete, using a child-centric approach, continues the research initiated in the Measuring Youth Wellbeing (MyWEB) and European Cohort Development (ECDP) projects, which will support elements of the preparatory phase of Europe's first cross-national accelerated birth cohort survey of child wellbeing: Growing Up in Digital Europe (GUIDE). GUIDE was included in the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) 2021 Roadmap.

SSHOC Insight

- ➔ Connection to leading Europe-wide social science research infrastructures
- ➔ Dialogue with Europe-wide survey data initiatives and discussions of future needs
- ➔ Access to state-of-the-art research in exploiting open cloud technologies
- ➔ Exemplars of practical open cloud data practices to ensure that data is fully compliant with FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles
- ➔ The future development of the GUIDE survey infrastructure will be shaped by techniques and protocols developed in SSHOC

Community Members

COORDINATE is led by [The Policy Evaluation and Research Unit at Manchester Metropolitan University](#), supported by [The Geary Institute at University College Dublin](#). It involves 22 partners from across Europe: <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/consortium>.

Within COORDINATE three complementary child wellbeing networks are being developed:

- ➔ Policy makers: <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/network>
- ➔ Scientists: <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/scientific-community>
- ➔ Youth Advisory Boards: <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/youth-advisory-board>

The COORDINATE project supports the development of the GUIDE study which includes further partners as shown here: <https://www.eurocohort.eu/project-partners/>

More Information

- ➔ COORDINATE animation: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w8RrJmazUqE>
- ➔ GUIDE animation: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kf9pjNjCWxE>
- ➔ Pitch events for transnational access research visits: <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/events-materials>

How to get involved?

Find out more and contact us at the following:

<https://www.coordinate-network.eu>

<https://www.coordinate-network.eu/newsletters>

Twitter: [@coordinate_eu](https://twitter.com/coordinate_eu)

coordinate@mmu.ac.uk

Access COORDINATE

Access directly

Data
Management

COORDINATE

Community

SurveyCodings

Socio-economic and more general social science variables are widely used in research. However, these variables cannot be measured with scales but require detailed and elaborate categorical classification systems. Some variables also come along with a larger number of answer categories challenging their measurement. The developed tools reduce office coding, less harmonization logistics and save costs by linking survey questionnaires to databases to allow the coding of survey variables during the interview. Database lookups can either replace open questions that need to be post-coded or long-list questions. Tools for several variables are developed and extended within SSHOC and available at surveycodings.org.

What is SurveyCodings

Surveycodings is a free service for social science projects, data archives and researchers measuring individual and socio-economic variables. It provides a multilingual repository containing questionnaires, data collection tools, and coding frames based on standard statistical classifications for a large number of countries. SurveyCodings covers the following variables: occupation, industry, levels and fields of education, region, food groups, religions, cost of living, and marital status, all coded according to ruling standards.

The coding sets use standard classifications to organize and code information and to enable input harmonization at data collection stage resulting in more consistent data, especially for cross-national data collection. Our services aim at developing solutions for fast high quality cost-effective cross-national harmonized coding for key variables. The coding tools use a dictionary containing tens of thousands of entries about job titles, industry names, religions, and fields of education. In addition, we provide country-specific, structured lists of educational qualifications, religious denominations and occupations. The code frames are provided using international standardized classifications, so that they can be used in cross national surveys such as SHARE, ESS, EVS, GGP, ISSP.

These coding sets can be used for respondent's self-selection or interviewer's selection during computer-assisted survey. It is also possible to use the coding sets as a resource for post-coding of the answers, e.g. of open-ended questions in order to achieve harmonized comparable data. To have a closer look at the different coding sets, the webpage provides a database live search separately for each variable and a demo questionnaire including all variables.

Key features

- ➔ Provides measurement instruments for individual and socio-economic variables that can be implemented in surveys;
- ➔ Coding sets can also be used for post-coding;
- ➔ Users can download the coding sets, questionnaires, source codes and review background information;
- ➔ The sets for food items or religions will help respondents in surveys to easier identify how they spend their budget or identify their actual religion;
- ➔ Some coding sets can be linked in view of specific research questions, e.g. industries to occupations, occupations to education;
- ➔ Classifications can be applied to the complete set in one go;
- ➔ Ready to use detailed and comparable data for survey agencies;
- ➔ Coding sets can be used for deeply scrutinizing a single-country case or for comparing at a higher level multiple countries.

Benefits

- ➔ Standardized instruments lead to higher comparability of the data across surveys using these instruments. So far, surveys use standard classifications derived from quite different measurement instruments, which lead to inconsistent and not comparable data; Ex-ante structured modules in different modes and formats;
- ➔ Website's functionality can be stored in an app that can be used on a mobile device; The infrastructure offers the opportunity of keeping the coding sets updated if deemed necessary; Data can automatically be easier compared, and no office coding is needed to harmonize the data; There is no longer a need to ask respondents to find their occupations or religion in a limited set of aggregated categories;
- ➔ Zoomed insight into national key sectors.

Contributors

European Values Study & CentERdata - Tilburg University/ GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences / WageIndicator Foundation

Access SurveyCodings

[Access SurveyCodings](#)

[Access SurveyCodings on the SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

[SurveyCodings on the SSH Open Marketplace](#)

Processing & Analysis

SurveyCodings

Tool

Automatic Verification Tool (AVT)

Challenge

The process of translation verification in a complex survey usually takes a third of the time allocated for translation procedures and it costs a person-month for each language for a 90-minutes-long questionnaire. The aim of an automatic tool to verify translations is to help human verifiers to preserve high standards and low operational costs.

What is the AVT

The Automatic Verification Tool (AVT) enables the user to verify translations using Bilingual Word Embeddings and to report to the translators a set of translated items to be re-checked.

How it works

- ➔ The AVT imports the questions and makes use of a trained Bilingual Word Embeddings model.
- ➔ It generates the 10 best foreign language translations of each English word.
- ➔ If one of the best translations is in the human foreign language translation it marks the word pair as matched.
- ➔ By measuring the number of matched word pairs it estimates the translation quality.
- ➔ It stores the translation quality scores and reports them to the user.

Benefits

A word-to-word translation system in such an unsupervised manner allows the researcher to do the task without using parallel corpora, making the process more efficient and cost-saving.

Tool

More information

- ➔ To get an idea: [Demo](#)
- ➔ SSHOC deliverable: [D4.11](#)
- ➔ Realising EOSC: Virtual Conference with a Difference: [Presentation about the Automated translation Verification Tool](#)
- ➔ [Report about the AVT by Max Planck Institute for Social Law and Social Policy p. 263](#)

Who made the tool

Yichen Liu and Yuri Pettinicchi (SHARE/MPISOC)

Access the AVT

[Access the AVT](#)

[Access the AVT on the Software Catalogue](#)

[Access the AVT on the SSH Open Marketplace](#)

Processing and
Analysis

Tool

"RAISE" (Restore dAta Integration Suite)

The RESTORE data integration suite RAISE (Restore dAta Integration Suite) is a toolbox supporting Memory, Cultural, Research institutions and citizen scientists with an interest in historical sources from archives, libraries, and museum collections in the creation of a FAIR digital ecosystem for Humanities Research, fostering semantic interoperability of cataloging standards and research data opening and sharing. RAISE will make available different tools to collect, align, merge and transform heterogeneous datasets from different research fields within Digital Humanities and Heritage Science (e.g.: material history and culture, archeology, history of art, literary studies and philology, restoration and conservation studies) with the aim of producing integrated and interoperable data, representing different aspects of the tangible and intangible dimensions of Cultural Heritage.

The RAISE platform

RESTORE is a tool-pack that will help cultural heritage and heritage science professionals, institutions and researchers to successfully accomplish recovery, integration, accessibility and reuse of multi-format and standardized digital resources, based on FAIR data principles.

The RESTORE workflow consists of the main following steps:

- ➔ from native data formats, such as XML-EAD and EAC, ICCD, and TEI (to name a few) to a custom exchange format, with data represented in a tabular form;
- ➔ from the custom tabular format (CSV), used to map the partners' data and align the common core entities, to the RDF/TTL serialization;
 1. Partnership with GLAMs → Data Ingestion → **CKAN**
 2. Data conversion, XML to CSV → Parsing → **Python Algorithm (custom)**
 3. Data mapping and modeling to **CIDOC-CRM** entities and properties
 4. Data parsing, CSV to RDF → **Python Algorithm (custom) + 3M (Mapping Memory Manager)**
 5. RDF triple import → **VIRTUOSO Endpoint SPARQL (custom script)**
 6. Documentation of data processing → **Gogs + JupyterLab**
 7. Final visualization and data browsing → **VIRTUOSO Facets + LodLive View + EVT**

Such a digital ecosystem will allow users to get open access to a unique data lake, where both the original resources and their triples (RDF), could be visualized and, if needed, downloaded.

Key features

- ➔ Data ingestion, data mapping, data storage;
- ➔ Multiple inquiries information integration;
- ➔ Customized data parsing (data conversion from the XML format to CSV; conversion of selected tags into triples; export of selected data in the RDF (TTL) format (logic complies with CIDOC-CRM and with catalogographic standards' articulation);
- ➔ Data dissemination and browsing through user-friendly interfaces.

Benefits

- ➔ Application of advanced ICT in the Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science domains, for data integration and management in a digital ecosystem;
- ➔ Creation of a user-friendly and innovative access to data fruition establishing conditions for data understanding, integration and possibility of their fruitful reuse in public, science and research environments;

PROJECT STRENGTHS:

- ➔ Unique Data lake → clear Use case
- ➔ Data Management
- ➔ Data Mapping
- ➔ Data Browsing
- ➔ (multiple) Data visualization strategies: (Lod)view, EVT, original datasets

More information

- ➔ [Home page CKAN - RESTORE](#)
- ➔ [Explore GOGS - RESTORE](#)
- ➔ [Home page LodLive - RESTORE](#)
- ➔ [Virtuoso SPARQL Query Editor](#)
- ➔ [SSHOC MS49 Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot alpha release](#)

Who made the tool

RESTORE is a tool developed by the team of the CNR - OVI (Istituto Opera del Vocabolario italiano). The CNR - OVI Institute also coordinates the POR-FSE 2014-20 RESTORE project, co-funded by the Regione Toscana. The approach, the software components and the technological solutions developed for the POR-FSE 2014-20 RESTORE project are products of the SSHOC T9.4, which developed the digital infrastructure needed. In terms of user communities, the task pilot involves people and datasets coming from the following institutions: Archives (Prato State Archives); Museums (Museo di Palazzo Pretorio, Prato); OVI (Istituto Opera del Vocabolario Italiano) - Cnr (IT); Superintendencies (The Archival and Bibliographic Superintendency); Coordination Agencies (Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of Italian Libraries, ICCU); Multiple research institutes in the field of Heritage Science and SSH, both within academic departments or research infrastructures active at a national level.

Access RESTORE

The RESTORE digital ecosystem will allow users to get open access to a unique data lake, where both the original resources and their triples (RDF), could be visualized, queried and, if needed, downloaded. The integrated datasets will be made accessible via the RESTORE SPARQL Endpoint: <http://dev.restore.ovi.cnr.it:8890/sparql/>.

[Access RESTORE
Interface for end-users](#)

[RESTORE Landing page](#)

[Access RESTORE on the
Service Catalogue](#)

Datasets

Pipeline

SSHOC
social sciences & humanities open cloud

Datasets

Multilingual Technologies for Open Science

Many different domains lack multilingual terminological resources. Making data and services accessible and usable in SSH is very much a matter of providing terminology across languages and multilingual vocabularies. Shortage of multilingual terminologies and vocabularies represents an obstacle to the access and reuse of information. Using the appropriate vocabularies can greatly improve both discovery and classification. Consequently, for SSHOC, it is important to address this issue with respect to the SSH domain. For the development of the European Open Science Cloud, terminologies pertaining to data management are recognized as particularly important, as they can be used to enrich datasets descriptions but also other types of documentation. The topic of Data Curation and Stewardship in particular, is of the utmost importance to all research infrastructures operating within the framework of the EOSC.

The challenge was: to investigate, first, how and to what extent language technologies (in this specific case, tools for automatic term extraction and machine translation) can assist in the creation of domain-specific terminologies, specifically a multilingual terminology in the domain of Data Stewardship; secondly, to integrate the extracted, validated and translated terms in existing lexical-semantic/terminological/ontological resources, with the goal of providing background resources to be used for the basic access functionalities.

Resource description

The Multilingual Data Stewardship Terminology collects terms pertaining to the domain of Data Stewardship. It is composed of 210 concepts, each assigned at least one label indicating what the concept indicates. If a concept can be referred to by using different terms, these alternate labels are specified as well. This applies, for instance, to synonyms (e.g. data citation – citation of data) and spelling variants (anonymisation - anonymization). These labels have been obtained by performing an automatic extraction of key terms from a domain-specific corpus collecting technical documents and standards on Data Stewardship and Curation. Extracted terms have then been validated by domain experts. Each concept is also assigned a definition, whose source is provided as well. If an equivalent concept is found in other existing terminologies, the concept is linked to it; the linking has been carried out with respect to the Loterre Open Science Thesaurus, the terms4FAIRskills terminology, the Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) and ISO. If an exact match with an existing concept is not found, a link with a broader concept can be provided.

For each concept, its label(s) and definition have been automatically translated into different languages (Dutch, French, German, Greek, Italian, Slovenian) by employing the Machine Translation tool Deep-L, and then manually checked by domain experts who are also native speakers of each language.

Dataset

Benefits and Findings

- ➔ How can Multilingual Data Stewardship Terminology help?
 - ➔ Multilingual Data Stewardship Terminology facilitate knowledge discovery, classification, and access to SSH content, by making content searchable across different languages
 - ➔ It can help define a common and standard terminology in the Data Stewardship domain; it contributes to creating and assessing data stewardship curricula, annotating FAIR-enabling training material, and formalising job descriptions with competencies
- ➔ How can NLP techniques and MT approaches help create new multilingual terminological resources?
 - ➔ Automatic Term Extraction and MT make a significant contribution to the creation of multilingual resources. Yet, results need to be checked: domain experts, also having knowledge of the topic, are necessary for validation.

More Information

Multilingual terminologies are available both in tabular format (CSV) and as a SKOS resource from the ILC4CLARIN repository

Frontini, Francesca; Gamba, Federica; Monachini, Monica; Broeder, Daan, 2021, SSHOC Multilingual Data Stewardship Terminology, ILC-CNR for CLARIN-IT, ILC-CNR for CLARIN-IT repository hosted at Institute for Computational Linguistics "A. Zampolli", National Research Council, in Pisa, <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-567>.

They can also be explored online from the SSHOC Vocabularies Platform:

<https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/vocabularies/sshocterm/>

A complete description of the translation and validation of the terminologies can be found in D3.9.

Access

[Service Catalogue](#)

[Data Access](#)

[SSHOC Vocabularies Access](#)

Datasets

Dataset

Datasets

Multilingual
Corpus of Survey
Questionnaires

Dataset

The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires (MCSQ)

Multilingual social surveys have become the main source of data to conduct cross-national comparative research. Translation procedures are transitioning to a larger adoption of Computer-Assisted Translation tools, which require the creation of text data.

The MCSQ corpus, the very first publicly available multilingual corpus of international survey texts, performs several functions. It enables the storing, searching and the comparison of information from international social surveys in 9 languages (e.g. French) and 29 of their language varieties (e.g. Swiss French).

The MCSQ constitutes an important new corpus for social scientists, linguists, translators and other interested parties. It has the potential to revolutionize survey research and design by allowing the researcher to consult both previous versions of surveys and also harmonize the same question across languages and language varieties. The Ask the same question method (ASQ) is at the heart of survey design. In the ASQ method, the translated questions in a multilingual survey are supposed to be functionally equivalent for the purpose of statistical analysis, that is, the data should be statistically comparable across linguistic groups. In the ASQ model, the concepts to be measured and the answer options are kept the same across languages, and cultural adaptation is only implemented to facilitate fluency and the use of locally appropriate terminology. Previously there has been no corpus available for ensuring that the same question is asked, and the MCSQ was compiled to fill this function.

Functionalities of the corpus

- ➔ The MCSQ functions both as a repository of previous rounds of surveys and a corpus for systematic analysis of previous errors and successes.
- ➔ The corpus allows for the retrieval and preservation of source and translated questionnaires, and provides textual data for survey translation activities, research and training.
- ➔ The corpus facilitates the visualization and statistical analysis of previous translation decisions across languages. It is also possible to assess in a comparative perspective how a term or a collection of terms have been translated across different languages and in different contexts, and analyze retrospectively whether this decision was appropriate to communicate the intended source text message.
- ➔ The MCSQ also allows for the integration of translation analysis into the design of the source questionnaire.
- ➔ The corpus provides valuable training material for the highly specialized field of survey design and translation.

Benefits

The MCSQ is an open-access, open-source research and training resource. It is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reproducible) by design. The current version (version 3.0) named (Rosalind Franklin), is composed of 306 distinct questionnaires comprising approximately 766.000 sentences. Nearly 88% of the corpus is sentence aligned, meaning that the source text sentences in English are linked to their translations in the different languages. In total, it is compiled from the following surveys and their versions:

- ➔ European Social Survey (ESS): Round 1, Round 2, Round 3, Round 4, Round 5, Round 6, Round 7, Round 8, Round 9
- ➔ Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) Round 7, Round 8 and COVID-19 questionnaire
- ➔ European Values Study (EVS): Wave 2, Wave 3, Wave 4, Wave 5
- ➔ WageIndicator: Round 1 and COVID-19 questionnaire

The surveys are available in English language and their translations into different languages (the availability of the language varies from the survey and its version): Catalan, Czech, French (localized language varieties for France, Switzerland, Belgium and Luxembourg), German (localized for Austria, Germany, Switzerland and Luxembourg), Norwegian (Bokmål), Portuguese (localized for Portugal), Spanish (localized for Spain) and Russian (localized for Belarus, Estonia, Israel, Latvia, Lithuania, Russia and Ukraine).

More information

- ➔ <https://www.upf.edu/web/mcsq/>
- ➔ [Manual; Presentation](#)
- ➔ [SSHOC Deliverable 4.3 Survey specific parallel corpora](#)
- ➔ [MCSQ Version v2.0 \(Mileva Marić-Einstein\)](#)
- ➔ [Blogpost](#)
- ➔ [MCSQ version 3.0 \(Rosalind Franklin\)](#)
- ➔ [The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires \(MCSQ\) at European Survey Research Association \(ESRA\) Conference 2021](#)

Who made the tool

Diana Zavala-Rojas (European Social Survey ERIC, Universitat Pompeu Fabra), Danielly Sorato (Universitat Pompeu Fabra), Lidun Hareide (Moreforskning Research Institute in Norway), Knut Hofland (University of Bergen). The use of the MCSQ data is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International License](#). The use of the MCSQ software and source code is licensed under EUPL-1.2 ([European Union Public License](#)).

Access the MCSQ

[Access the MCSQ directly](#)

[Access via the SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

Datasets

Multilingual
Corpus of Survey
Questionnaires

Dataset

CLARIN Multilingual Metadata

Multilingual Search for Tools and Resources

Terminological resources are mostly described in English only, regardless of the domain. This issue constitutes an obstacle to the access and reuse of information: in this way, such resources are easily available to English native speakers but could prove less straightforward to find to researchers and users speaking different languages, meaning that content is not truly available to all in an equal manner. Multilingual metadata terms and vocabularies are thus meant to provide multilingual access to content across different languages and to improve discovery of resources and tools by non-native English speakers.

What is the Resource for?

The CLARIN Multilingual Metadata resource translates into different languages the set of 232 approved metadata from the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR), which are originally available in English. Together with metadata, their definitions are translated as well.

CLARIN metadata aims at describing language resources. In particular, they are meant to map and harmonise metadata from various centres in the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO). Translating such metadata and their definitions allows to describe in many languages the different resources in the VLO, developed by different researchers from different countries, and to pursue the harmonisation intent with a multilingual approach. In this way, non-native English speakers will be able to describe their resources more easily, as they can adopt their own language. Similarly, SSH researchers will be able to find and access such resources in a simpler way.

Resource Description

The CCR 232 approved metadata and their definition are translated into four languages, namely Dutch, French, Greek and Italian. Translations are obtained by exploiting state-of-the-art Machine Translation tools (Deep-L, Google Translate, LINDAT Translation, Reverso) and manually checked by domain experts that are native speakers of the language.

Benefits

The lack of multilingual terminological resources in different domains constitutes an obstacle to the access and reuse of information.

➔ How can multilingual metadata concepts help?

Dataset

- ➔ Multilingual metadata concepts provide multilingual access to content across different languages and highly enhance discoverability of resources in the SSH by non-native speakers; SSH researchers can easily manage a wider range of SSH content.
- ➔ Can Machine Translation tools offer an effective solution to metadata concepts translation?
 - ➔ Machine Translation tools perform well, although their results need to undergo validation.

Datasets

More Information

Multilingual metadata are available both in tabular format (CSV) and as a SKOS resource from the ILC4CLARIN repository.

Frontini, Francesca; Gamba, Federica; Monachini, Monica; Broeder, Daan, 2021, SSHOC Multilingual Metadata, ILC-CNR for CLARIN-IT repository hosted at Institute for Computational Linguistics "A. Zampolli", National Research Council, in Pisa, <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-568>.

➔ They can also be explored online from the SSHOC Vocabularies Platform:

➔ <https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/vocabularies/sshocmm/>

A complete description of the translation and validation of the metadata can be found in D3.9.

Dataset

Access CLARIN Multilingual Metadata

[Data Access](#)

Data are deposited in the ILC4CLARIN centre

[SSHOC Vocabularies access](#)

Data can be navigated and accessed through the Vocabulary Commons SKOSMOS platform

I The SSH Training Community

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud project (SSHOC) is designed to achieve a great vision: Creating the Social Sciences and Humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in a fully digital cloud-based infrastructure. Undoubtedly, people are at the center of SSHOC: researchers, IT developers, trainers, librarians, repository managers and many more that are both users and contributors. They share a common goal: conducting FAIR and meaningful research, developing supportive tools and services, and connecting people with a passion for the SSH from all over Europe. Thus, providing training resources, creating an interactive training network, and offering training activities are three crucial aspects to the success of this pan-European project. To make this complex task work, a collaboration mechanism is needed with which knowledge can be gathered and shared. In order to facilitate such exchange and connection in the field of training and education, SSHOC has established the SSH Training Community with its various formats. The community makes training resources available for reuse, facilitates exchange between trainers from the Social Sciences and Humanities as well as between those who wish to receive training, e.g. in the field of data stewardship.

The Training Community provides a platform that brings together trainers who are involved in providing training activities for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) scholars. It allows multiple interactive formats of exchange for professionals from various countries, backgrounds, sub-domains and levels of expertise. The interaction is facilitated through monthly calls, dedicated events and a joint mailing list.

Key features

The SSH Training Community is a platform that is open to anyone with an interest in training in the field of the SSH. It is not restricted to Europe although most members come from the EU area. Monthly digital meetings were organized for training community members where various topics were discussed. Members could address topics themselves and provide their own perspective, sharing their knowledge and expertise about a given topic. Materials were shared with all community members through a dedicated online drive. Next to the meetings, a dedicated mailing list was set up where members could share information about events or other activities.

Benefits

The SSH Training Community

- ➔ allows trainers to stay connected
- ➔ gives the opportunity for interaction and exchange between training professionals
- ➔ provides trainers with materials they can re-use in their own trainings
- ➔ allows the SSHOC training team to receive feedback on tools and events from the wider community

More information

The [SSHOC website](#) contains background information about the SSH Training Community. The community has been presented at various occasions throughout the project including the [Realising the EOSC event in 2020](#) and more recently during the [Open Science Fair in 2021](#). More information on the Training Community is available in [D6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community](#).

Who made the tool

The Training Community was coordinated by Task 6.4 of SSHOC WP6. In particular DANS, LIBER, GESIS and Trust-IT contributed to the organisation of the community and related events.

Access the SSH Training Community

[Access the Training Community](#)

Training and Support

Community

SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

A lack of quick availability of relevant training materials often limits Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) trainers in developing training activities and programmes. The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit addresses this gap by improving the discoverability and providing access to effective and often ready-to-use training resources. In the long run, we hope the tool will make providing training on Open Science, Research Data Management, FAIR and open data easier to all European SSH communities, thus supporting the shift of the current research culture towards Open Science.

What is the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit ("Toolkit" in short) is an inventory of various learning and training materials that trainers of different disciplines in the SSH can use to find materials for re-use in their own training activities. The Toolkit links to a variety of materials available through various sources on topics including Open Science, Research Data Management, and didactics, but also specific topics that are relevant to multiple disciplines, like text encoding and spatial data. The Toolkit is continuously being updated and currently contains more than 240 items from more than 95 different sources on the above-mentioned topics for better development and implementation of training activities.

Key features

While it primarily targets trainers, the Toolkit also contains links to training materials targeting other audiences available for the SSH communities. The Toolkit is designed in close collaboration with the [SSH Training Community](#) to make available training resources discoverable and encourage re-use and exchange.

The Toolkit offers a collection of example materials which are described using metadata and a set of controlled vocabularies that can be used to filter and structure the information.

Benefits

- ➔ The Toolkit helps to make the process of training preparation and delivery more efficient and effective.
- ➔ The Toolkit is curated, which means it is continuously improved in its content and functionality, based on the feedback from trainers (users) and the SSH Training Community.

- ➔ The Toolkit is also being updated taking into consideration the work and recommendations of other international initiatives including the EOSC working group on skills and training, as well as the RDA IG Education and Training on handling of Research Data (ETHRD) and the EOSC Future project.
- ➔ The collected metadata for the various training resources will be aligned with metadata models developed within the EOSC and dedicated Research Data Sharing (RDA) groups to ensure that the information in the Toolkit is interoperable and can be integrated into other services.

Training and Support

More Information

- ➔ [D6.7 Inventory of existing learning materials](#)
- ➔ [D6.9 SSHOC Trainer Toolkit \(draft\)](#)
- ➔ [MS39 Launch expertise strategy](#)
- ➔ [MS40 SSHOC Training Toolkit \(preliminary version\)](#)
- ➔ [Training Discovery Toolkit Poster](#)

Who made the tool

All partners involved in the SSHOC Task on Building Expertise: the SSHOC Training network (Lead: KNAW(DANS), Partners: LIBER, CESSDA/GESIS, CESSDA/UKDA, CLARIN/UL-FF, UCL), provided the curated content with input from the SSH Training Community. Task 6.3 Empowering Users: Training Materials and Online Learning Paths (Lead: DARIAH/OEAW; Partners: DARIAH ERIC, CLARIN ERIC, CLARIN/UL-FF, CESSDA/NSD, CESSDA/UKDA, UCL, CNR) developed, maintained, and updated the tool.

Training

Access the Training Discovery Toolkit

[Access the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit](#)

[SSH Training Toolkit on the SSH Open Marketplace](#)

Trainers Directory

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud project (SSHOC) is designed to achieve a great vision: Creating the Social Sciences and Humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in a fully digital cloud-based infrastructure. Undoubtedly, people are at the center of SSHOC: researchers, IT developers, trainers, librarians, repository managers and many more that are both users and contributors. They share a common goal: conducting FAIR and meaningful research, developing supportive tools and services, and connecting people with a passion for the SSH from all over Europe. Thus, creating an interactive training network is a crucial aspect to the success of this pan-European project. To make this complex task work, a collaboration mechanism is needed with which knowledge can be gathered and shared. In order to facilitate such exchange and connection in the field of training and education, SSHOC has established the SSH [Training Community with its various formats](#) and a so-called [Trainers Directory](#).

The Trainers Directory is a database where trainers and experts in the field of SSH are listed. Individuals or organisations who are interested in providing training, and those who wish to find suitable experts in various topics can use the directory (i.e. Research Data Management or Open Science). The tool contains a pool of qualified and experienced trainers—often members of the SSH Training Community—who are enthusiastic to bring people interested in training to the next level of their expertise in a specific sub-domain.

Key features

Through the directory, trainers can be found and approached by individuals or organisations looking for trainers in the field of SSH. The public page of the directory shows the trainers' name and picture as well as the discipline. Trainers can be filtered by target audience, domain, spoken language, and level of training they provide. For each trainer, a more detailed profile is available after registering on the SSHOC website. The profile offers additional information like the trainers ORCID ID, their qualifications and languages and information about a selection of training activities. Trainers can be contacted through his or her profile page.

Benefits

The Trainers Directory:

- ➔ provides an overview of active trainers in the SSH field in one online environment
- ➔ allows anyone to find a trainer in the field of SSH with expertise in given areas
- ➔ helps trainers to be more visible and promote their work
- ➔ contributes to the distribution of knowledge and training on responsible science

Tool

More information

The Trainers Directory is available on the [SSHOC website](#). A more detailed [presentation](#) on the directory was held during a monthly Training Community Call. The development of the Trainers Directory will be described in D6.13 *Report on the SSHOC Training Community* (updated version to be published at the end of the project in April 2022).

Who made the tool

The Trainers Directory was developed as part of Task 6.4 of SSHOC WP6. In particular GESIS, DANS, LIBER and Trust-IT contributed to its development.

Access the Trainers Directory

[Access the Trainers Directory](#)

Training and Support

Tool

Improved and FAIR data Repositories – SSHOC Trusted Repositories (SSHOC Trust Support)

Trust is crucial when providing data preservation and reuse services. Research data should be managed, curated, stored and shared in a way that meets stakeholders' and users' expectations regarding trustworthiness and quality, provides sustainability, and preserves the investments made in digital assets. Trust between all parties in the quality of data and services is critical for data repositories and research infrastructure in terms of people, processes and technologies.

Certification as a trustworthy digital repository is one way to demonstrate reliability and build trust. However, many data repositories interested in showcasing their trustworthiness through certification are not familiar with the process or lack the resources and capabilities for certification on their own. Therefore, they benefit from support in issues and questions related to certification.

SSHOC Trust Support promotes trust and quality assurance by supporting selected data repositories in their journey to get the CoreTrustSeal certification. Trust Support allows the supported repositories to consult experts on repository certification, align their practices to respond to the standards expected from trustworthy repositories, receive comments on their self-assessment drafts, and provide feedback on the certification process and requirements to enable developing certification further in the future. The support team provides assistance to the repositories all the way to submitting the formal CoreTrustSeal application. Furthermore, SSHOC Trust Support also provides resources related to trust and certification and organises events on the topic.

Key features

Trust Support is provided in the following forms:

- ➔ One-on-one meetings between the members of the SSHOC support team and the representatives of repositories that applied for support.
- ➔ Providing comments and feedback from the support team on the self-assessments of the supported repositories.
- ➔ Workshops and webinars on trust and certification.
- ➔ Webpage on certification and trust with resources for repositories seeking certification

Support

Benefits

- ➔ Improved practices of repositories, as trusted digital repositories enable access to FAIR data over time.
- ➔ Increased visibility of trust and quality issues and raised awareness of the added value of the SSHOC tools.
- ➔ Access to secure and trusted repositories by identifying these to researchers, funders and other stakeholders.
- ➔ Promotion of open science, FAIR data and principles, and contribution to the increased visibility of research data to the scientific community.
- ➔ Experiences and lessons learned from the support process to develop certification and consider future cooperation and networks related to trustworthy digital repositories.

More information

- ➔ [SSHOC D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories](#)
- ➔ [SSHOC WEBINAR: How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories](#)
- ➔ [YouTube: DARIAH Virtual Annual Event: Building trustworthy repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal certification](#)

Who made the tool

SSHOC Trust Support is provided by the SSHOC Task 8.2 team: Mari Kleemola (CESSDA/FSD), Tuomas Alaterä (CESSDA/FSD), Henri Ala-Lahti (CESSDA/FSD), Birger Jerlehag (CESSDA/SND), Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Tomasz Parkoła (DARIAH-PSNC), René van Horik (KNAW/DANS), Hervé L'Hours (CESSDA/UKDS), Benjamin Mathers (CESSDA/UKDS), Maurizio Sanesi (CNR) and Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (CNR).

Access the SSHOC Trust Support

[Access the SSHOC Trust Support](#)

Training and Support

Support

SSHOC League of Data

Data Management Challenge

The SSHOC League of Data (SSHOC LoD) is a pilot gamification of the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide® (DMEG). The game supports and motivates researchers to publish their research data by providing guidance for the publishing process. The game takes a researcher through various concepts, fears and challenges associated with publishing data in an interesting and fun way. The goal is to check the knowledge gained. The game can be used as an addition to the educational process or as a self-assessment tool. The SSHOC LoD is a pilot version for the CESSDA DMEG chapters on archiving, publishing and protecting data.

Data publishing is becoming a standard required by funders and scientific journals. Experience shows that there is still a lot of hesitation with publishing data and other outcomes of the surveys. Investment in efforts to raise awareness and train researchers through a variety of channels is needed. The CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide® was designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The SSHOC LoD has turned the few chapters into a fun and light-weight learning experience for researchers dealing with the management of their data. SSHOC Insight

The SSHOC LoD and its first pilot game Data Management Challenge is designed to inspire and guide researchers in how to publish one's research data. The game presents challenges that researchers encounter in the process of data publication in a playful way. From resolving legal and ethical challenges in the data collection phase, to learning the difference between

LEAGUE OF DATA

Game

publishing or just archiving the data. We argue the benefits of sharing the data and end the game by introducing different promotional possibilities which are the ones usually forgotten by researchers.

Key features

- ➔ Freely available online.
- ➔ Game version of the DMEG chapters Publish & Archive and Protect.
- ➔ Every game level represents a specific topic of how to protect, publish and archive your social science and humanities research data.

Benefits

- ➔ Inspires researchers in a fun way to learn about the many aspects of archiving and publishing in research data management.
- ➔ Researchers overcome their fears related to managing the archiving and publishing of their research data.
- ➔ A game used in training.
- ➔ Help data service providers raise awareness of the topic of research data management.

More information

Reference for the content of the game: Data Management Expert Guide - CESSDA.eu/DMEG

Code is published under Open Source licence and available for anyone to implement their own content.

Who made the tool

SHOCC partners CESSDA and Trust-IT have joined efforts to create the SSHOC LoD, based on the CESSDA DMEG®, and designed to service the needs of researchers and trainers from the Social Sciences and Humanities and beyond.

Access the SSHOC League of Data

[Direct Access](#)

[Access via the Service Catalogue](#)

Training and Support

LEAGUE OF DATA

Game

Archaeology Data Service / Digital Antiquity Guides to Good Practice

Challenge

Much of the information produced by archaeological research exists in lengthy, and limited-distribution reports, tables etc. in offices. The data contained in these resources are often encoded in e.g. computer cards that are degrading in archives, museums etc. The most common preservation treatment for digital data is to conserve the media on which the digital files are stored. Unfortunately, this method presents problems, such as the fact that the data on such media renders inaccessible because the needed hardware and software for these tasks is rapidly disappearing in many cases.

What are the Guides to Good Practice

Modern archaeological projects have the capacity to create large quantities of digital information, whether from the on-site recording of excavation and survey data, specialist datasets developed during pre and post-excavation analysis, or publication of interpretative maps and plans. Digital information is created at every stage of a project, from fieldwork to assessment, analysis, and finally reporting and dissemination. Within the discipline, there has been an increasing awareness that data, not just artefacts and paper records, are part of the primary collection and should be preserved and archived as such. The current trend of moving away from physical and toward digital recording of information has made the lack of thoughtful preservation of digital data an even larger issue. In fact, in many cases, a digital dataset may be the only product of a project, and without thoughtful preservation, all context for any archaeological resources will be lost.

Key features

The Guides cover “basic components,” i.e. common file types that are frequently present in archaeological archives, irrespective of a project’s primary technique or focus. The chapters cover a range of file types, including documents and texts, databases, spreadsheets, raster and vector images and digital audio and video files. Although these file types have been isolated here, in many cases such files can feed into or be the product of other techniques or applications that are discussed elsewhere in the Guides. In such cases, links with the relevant chapters are included so that the way in which these “basic components” fit in and relate to other data types is made clear.

In addition, the core chapters of these new Guides address the preservation of data resulting from common data collection, processing and analysis techniques such as aerial

Training

and geophysical survey, laser scanning, GIS and CAD. As with the basic components, these chapters largely deal with each technique as a workflow in isolation but link, where relevant, to other chapters where certain data can be seen as a discrete input or output.

Benefits

Archaeology is in a special position with respect to archiving because archaeological fieldwork, which creates archaeological data, also destroys the primary in situ archaeological evidence itself. Increasingly, the digital record may be the only source of information about archaeological research materials. It is essential, therefore, that the digital records that describe archaeological resources be made accessible and that their preservation be ensured. Providing for the accessibility of archaeological data and its long-term preservation are the goals of digital archiving.

More information

How to use the Guides to Good Practice:

<https://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/UsingGuides>

Who made the tool

This Guides to Good Practice were produced as the result of a two-year collaborative project between the UK Archaeology Data Service and Digital Antiquity in the US. The project involved previous Guides authors revising existing content alongside new authors, from both Europe and the US, also contributing to the development of the guides into new themes and areas. Other projects where ADS was a partner have also fed into the revision and development of the Guides.

Access the Guides

[Access the Guides to Good Practice](#)

[Access the Guides on the Service Catalogue](#)

Training and Support

Training

Religious Studies

What is the Religious Studies Community

Religious studies research demands a specific approach due to the scientific questions and technological challenges posed by the way research is conducted by the community. In order to share expertise, provide high-quality research data and develop tools and services related to the study of religion, the Religious Studies community is developing its own research infrastructure - RESILIENCE (Religious Studies Infrastructure: toolS, Innovation, Experts, conNections and Centres in Europe). RESILIENCE entered the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Roadmap (ESFRI RM) in 2021 and started its preparatory phase to become a research infrastructure in 2022.

RESILIENCE is the latest step of a European partnership built on both national and European projects, including the ReIReS starting community. That community of twelve European institutions had started to build a, so far, unique and highly qualified research infrastructure on religious studies. ReIReS has laid the foundations for a research infrastructure that is further developed by RESILIENCE. In the process, the European Academy of Religion, established by 506 universities in 2015, serves as an exchange platform for various stakeholders: scholars, universities, research centres, research infrastructures, scientific journals and publishers – coming not only from Europe, but also from surrounding countries.

Currently, RESILIENCE faces two major challenges: first, the establishment of the research infrastructure as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), and second, matching the needs of its scientific community with an efficient and accessible collection of services and tools. However, those challenges are to be addressed by the Consortium of 13 partners as they share the belief that the RESILIENCE research infrastructure has a highly positive impact on the research field of Religious Studies, and therefore, fosters the understanding of religion within society.

SSHOC Insight

Through the participating partners FSCIRE and InfAI, SSHOC offered RESILIENCE a big window of opportunity due to the main goal of the SSHOC project: developing a shared cloud for the SSH. RESILIENCE can contribute to that platform and will be certainly enriched by data coming from the domain of Religious Studies. Following the work of WP9 on Data Communities was a learning experience and showed the complexities of the work conducted on diverse community datasets. The most relevant impact SSHOC will have on RESILIENCE is the way how RESILIENCE will plan its service strategy and design.

Community Members

RESILIENCE is led by FSCIRE (Fondazione per le scienze religiose, Italy), which became a SSHOC partner in 2021, together with another RESILIENCE member institution, InfAI (Institut für Angewandte Informatik, Germany). The research infrastructure consortium is built on 13 academic and research partners based in 11 countries:

- ➔ [Albanian University](#), Albania
- ➔ [Bar Ilan University](#), Israel
- ➔ [Cineca Consorzio Interuniversitario](#), Italy
- ➔ [École Pratique des Hautes Études](#), France

- ➔ [Fondazione per le scienze religiose Giovanni XXIII](#) (Coordinator), Italy
- ➔ [Institut für Angewandte Informatik](#), Germany
- ➔ [KU Leuven](#), Belgium
- ➔ [Sofia University](#), Bulgaria
- ➔ [Theological University of Apeldoorn](#), the Netherlands
- ➔ [University of Münster](#), Germany
- ➔ [University of Sarajevo](#), Bosnia and Herzegovina
- ➔ [University of Warsaw](#), Poland
- ➔ [Volos Academy for Theological Studies](#), Greece

More information

Recordings of RESILIENCE webinars as well as other videos are available YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC3DBKl9jzFyFibWhAWyx5Sw/videos>

The RelResearch database, part of the RESILIENCE service catalogue, is accessible via <https://reiresearch.eu/>.

How to get involved?

- ➔ Website: <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/>
- ➔ Newsletter subscription: <https://resilience-ri.us4.list-manage.com/subscribe/post?u=0583cb89c3e930687bf22483e&id=4d50efc77b>
- ➔ Social media channels: <https://www.facebook.com/resilienceRI/> https://www.instagram.com/resilience_ri/ <https://twitter.com/resilienceRI> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/resilience-ri/>
- ➔ Contact Coordinator Fscire: resilience@fscire.it.

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Access Resilience

[Access Resilience](#)

Training and
Support

RESILIENCE

Community

OPERAS

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH. OPERAS' aim is to make Open Science a reality for research in the SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and more generally the whole society across Europe and worldwide, without barriers.

What is the OPERAS community

OPERAS community gathers researchers, universities, publishers, and infrastructures of the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) area aiming at building together a comprehensive and functional environment for the open scholarly communication. Convinced that scholarly communication, from the traditional publication to more innovative communication objects and tools, is at the heart of research, the community organized itself to address specific challenges. SSH community offers a scattered landscape, divided in many disciplines, strongly connected to national or local networks, using a high diversity of languages. The community's outputs can, therefore, hardly use the global pathways to reach high visibility, which is generally dependent on the use of English, the dissemination through journals with high impact-factor. To address these challenges, the community needs support to share good practices and knowledge about standardization that will increase its integration in the global digital environment. It also needs appropriate infrastructures taking into account its specificities, like for instance multilingualism or domain vocabularies.

SSHOC Insight

The main impact of SSHOC achievements concerns the OPERAS project TRIPLE, dedicated to the creation of a discovery platform for the Social Sciences and Humanities: the GoTriple platform. GoTriple indexed publications and datasets and it made use of data catalogs created within SSHOC, like for instance the data collections from CESSDA and CLARIN.Community Members.

Community Members

OPERAS core members are the following:

- ➔ Max Weber Stiftung (DEU)
- ➔ CNRS (FRA)
- ➔ EKT (GRE)
- ➔ Univ. of Zadar (HRV)
- ➔ Univ. of Turin (ITA)
- ➔ OAPEN (NLD)
- ➔ IBL-PAN (POL)
- ➔ Univ. of Coimbra (PRT)
- ➔ ZRC SAZU (SVN)
- ➔ Jisc (GBR)

OPERAS community main targets are: Open Access publishers (university presses, SMEs, platforms) and Social Sciences and Humanities researchers (authors, editors, digital humanists, etc.)

Training and
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How to get involved?

- ➔ Contact: www.operas-eu.org
- ➔ Join our newsletter: <https://www.operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter/>
- ➔ Twitter: [@OPERASEU](https://twitter.com/OPERASEU)

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"Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782

SSHOC
social sciences & humanities open cloud

DARIAH-IT
Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

IPERION HS

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Heritage Science and Humanities Data Community

The Heritage Science and Humanities Data Community involves cultural heritage experts and scientists from a range of disciplines – digital humanists, conservators, literary scholars, historians and art historians, archaeologists, architects, chemists, physicists, material scientists, engineers - to name only a few -, who collaborate in the new multidisciplinary field of digital heritage science and humanities, integrating and sharing data across the fields. The data community gathers around existing resources belonging to the domains of digital arts and humanities, such as:

- lists, collections, datasets, reference tools, glossaries, archival and library records, digital editions of works of philology or records with a philological and lexicographical focus (i.e. digital lexicography);
- records of written or iconic resources and/or other specific documentation formats regarding artworks, catalogs and other museum resources; available digital samples and datasets and/or materials related to the study and the analysis of physical objects and artifacts linked to the fields of archaeology, architecture, visual studies, technical art history.

The ample range of disciplines covered by the community is a testimony of the need of building common protocols and strategies based on existing data and metadata standards, already developed in each scientific discipline, for the reuse and sharing of existing technologies rather than creating new semantic structures, authority tables and linked data. The data community objective was to cover the heterogeneous data landscape made of a mix of structured, tabular, unstructured and semi-structured data, towards an interoperable and common set of tools, practices, standard, policies. The E-RIHS partners - GLAM institutions such as National Archives, Libraries, Research Institutes and Museums - provided datasets composed of data which have been created and structured according to a consistent variety of standards and internal procedures. Those data were ingested and made interoperable through mapping and modeling processes based on a common ontology also in use within the general SSHOC Community (CIDOC-CRM). The pilot use case comprehended both cultural heritage (CH) datasets (documents, texts, works of art, manuscripts, and artifacts) and heritage science (HS) datasets (high-resolution measures and analyses made on artistic objects).

SSHOC Insight

The data community performed joint initiatives towards the mapping and pooling of governance-related activities across the SSHOC project. With references to the workflows and tools developed by the data community within SSHOC, a user-friendly semantic data (and graph) navigation tool, such as LODLive, helped domain experts from the Heritage Science community to evaluate the efficiency of the data integration strategy adopted: checking the information needed to be visible and communicated to both academic and general end users, such as information about physical supports, relevant for users interested in the tangible characteristics of Cultural Heritage (i.e.: Heritage Scientists). The conceptual reference model and ontology (CIDOC-CRM) revealed itself as key to foster open access and FAIRification of the partners' data, without preferring specific and too narrow domain-related logics. The data communities, the HS, the CH and Social Sciences and Humanities researchers, both share use of the others' information related to tangible or intangible dimensions of cultural heritage.

With regard to the "RESTORE pilot" approach, the technological solutions developed, can be extended to other projects and reused in similar contexts by other institutions within the GLAMs, the Digital Humanities and Heritage Science research communities. Furthermore, the project's development benefits from the collaboration with DARIAH-ERIC (ESFRI Landmark for the humanities and social sciences) and E-RIHS (ESFRI project for heritage science), as well as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In this respect, the development of the RESTORE

Community

digital tool aligned with the SSHOC, and the IPERION-HS project's aims to deliver a toolkit for heterogeneous data modeling and integration, as well as to establish a set of good practices for the research data management and storage.

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Community Members

- ➔ DIGILAB Working Group (E-RIHS MOLAB testbed);
 - ➔ Contextual data provider: OVI-CNR and ISPC-CNR (ISPC: OAI_DC XML records harvested through OAI-PMH, PDF files of the Journal Issues; OVI: text-based resources, tagged textual corpora, vocabularies and dictionaries, archival descriptions (XML-EAD), EAC authority files)
 - ➔ E-RIHS partner (GLAMs such as National Archives, Libraries, Research Institutes and Museums);
- Long term sustainability of Heritage Science and Humanities Data Community is ensured by the maintenance of the data structure created in the context of the Data Centers already activated and texted (end of 2020) by the Italian node of DARIAH infrastructure (DARIAH.it). Those Data Centers are running and are in the stage of final definition.

More information

- ➔ [RESTORE Landing page](#)
- ➔ [IPERION-HS Service Catalog page](#)
- ➔ [DARIAH-IT Research Infrastructure Italian node](#)

How to get involved?

- ➔ DIGILAB Working Group: [MOLAB - Landing Page and contact information](#)
- ➔ CNR - [OVI - Research Infrastructures and contact page](#), [ISPC - contact page](#), [INO - contact page](#)
- ➔ E-RIHS partner ([GLAMs](#) such as National Archives, Libraries, Research Institutes and Museums);

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